

A synergistic effect of microwave irradiation and nano-TiO₂@[DABCO(CH₂CH₂CO₂H)]⁺[Br]⁻ for the expeditious synthesis of fully functionalised pyrroles incorporating benzo-thio unit[†]

Priya Mondal and Chhanda Mukhopadhyay*

Department of Chemistry, University of Calcutta, 92, Acharya Prafulla Chandra Road, Kolkata-700 009, India

E-mail: cmukhop@yahoo.co.in

Manuscript received online 21 November 2020, revised and accepted 30 December 2020

A quick access and sustainable strategy for the one-pot, solvent-free and chromatography free synthesis of the diversified N-aryl fully functionalised pyrroles incorporating benzo-thio unit is demonstrated here. Here synergistic effect of microwave irradiation and nano-TiO₂@[DABCO(CH₂CH₂CO₂H)]⁺[Br]⁻ has been utilised. The foremost objective of this work is to emphasize the environmentally benevolent and facile nature of the combined microwave-assisted quasi-heterogeneous catalytic methods.

Keywords: Microwave irradiation, nano-TiO₂@IL, pyrroles, synergistic effect, sustainable strategy.

Introduction

Over the years, significant effort has been committed to improve the laboratory protocols for convenient and rapid transformations considering environmental benignity in the field of organic, combinatorial and medicinal chemistry¹. Principles of green chemistry promoted by Anastas, suggested that microwave chemistry has a strong relevance with green chemistry². Microwave-assisted reactions carried out at an optimized reaction temperature have been revealed as more cleaner and leading to less by-products compared to the conventionally heated processes carried out at the reflux temperature of the solvent³. This lenient and green methodology is highly effective for the minimization of energy consumption and considerable reduction in reaction time compared to conventional synthesis. The conventional heating necessary 3–9 times further energy than the microwave assisted organic synthesis (MAOS)⁴.

Over the past few decades room temperature ionic liquids (ILs) are considered as very effective environment-friendly reaction media as well as catalyst due to their high boiling point and low vapour pressure nature⁵. Among various quaternary alkylammonium ILs, 1,4-diazobicyclo[2.2.2]octane (DABCO) derived ionic liquids have been shown to be very effective catalysts for many important reactions⁶. In

the recent time homogeneous ILs are not used alone as a catalyst, homogeneous ILs are loaded over heterogeneous metal or non-metal oxide nanoparticles to produce more effective quasi-heterogeneous catalyst⁷. This admired catalytic concept is known as Supported catalysts with an ionic liquid layer (SCILL) where ILs are immobilised as a thin layer over solid support⁸. Now, choice of TiO₂-NP as an inner core is advantageous in microwave assisted reaction as having high dielectric constant of almost 50, shows high absorption power of MW irradiation⁹. Highly ionic nature of DABCO based IL is also microwave-irradiation friendly.

Pyrrole moiety is one of the most valuable heterocyclic compound that have been found to be useful in many fields¹⁰. Pyrrole based compounds are not only found in many natural products¹¹ and pharmaceuticals¹² but are also extensively used in material science¹³ and supramolecular chemistry¹⁴. As a result of the significant importance of the pyrrole based heterocyclic compound, interest in the synthesis of new pyrrole compounds and improvement in the synthesis methodologies are cultivating for several years and that is continuing in recent time also.

Results and discussion

Considering biological importance of pyrrole moieties,

[†]Invited Lecture.

benzo-thio unit incorporating functionalised pyrroles have been tried to synthesis in more facile and environmentally benign way. Preliminary DABCO based mono-substituted amphoteric IL {[DABCO(CH₂CH₂COOH)]⁺[Br]⁻} was synthesised by reacting DABCO with one equivalent of 3-bromo propionic acid as precursor. In the next step, ionic liquid covered TiO₂ nanoparticles were synthesised by treating titanium tetraisopropoxide in hot ethanol with stabilising effect of IL. IL played role of "organic stencil" or structure-directing negotiator that controlled the development and function of TiO₂-NP. The schematic representation has been shown below (Scheme 1) and the details procedure has been described in Experimental section.

Scheme 1. Preparation of nano-TiO₂@[DABCO(CH₂CH₂COOH)]⁺[Br]⁻.

At first, formation of nano-TiO₂@[DABCO(CH₂CH₂COOH)]⁺[Br]⁻ was confirmed and characterized by FT-IR spectrum (Fig. 1) with a distinguishing absorption peak at 3432 cm⁻¹ and 1718 cm⁻¹ which are accredited to a stretching vibration of the hydroxyl group and carboxylic carbonyl

group of functionalized DABCO based IL respectively. The peaks in the region of 500 to 800 cm⁻¹, 1630 cm⁻¹ and 2985 cm⁻¹ credited to TiO₂-NP. According to the following FT-IR spectrum, formation of carboxylic acid group functionalised ionic liquid covered TiO₂-NP was established.

The morphology of the combined catalytic system (nano-TiO₂@[DABCO(CH₂CH₂COOH)]⁺[Br]⁻) was revealed by the following SEM image (Fig. 2). This image indicates that all the synthesised catalyst particles are of uniform sizes and the size of those catalysts were in the scale of 70 to 90 nm.

Few of the representative HRTEM images of the synthesised catalyst were shown in the following Fig. 3. These images were taken in different magnification to get the clear idea about surface modification. From these HRTEM images it was revealed that size of the catalyst was equivalent to data obtained from SEM image.

In order to synthesize the desired compounds in most facile way, it is really significant to control the reactions by choosing most suitable reaction conditions. For this reason, to optimize the reaction condition (Table 1) a series of synthesis works were carried out with a representative reaction of 4-chloro benzene thiol (1 mmol), phenyl glyoxal (1 mmol), para toluidine (1 mmol) and dimethyl acetylenedicarboxylate (1 mmol) with alteration of reaction parameters, such as solvent, catalyst, reaction temperature etc.

Fig. 1. FT-IR spectrum of the nano-TiO₂@[DABCO(CH₂CH₂COOH)]⁺[Br]⁻.

Fig. 2. SEM image of nano-TiO₂@[DABCO(CH₂CH₂COOH)]⁺[Br]⁻.

Fig. 3. HRTEM image of nano-TiO₂@[DABCO(CH₂CH₂COOH)]⁺[Br]⁻.

Although reactions were conducted both in conventional as well as microwave-irradiated condition our main concern was related to microwave assisted reaction. At first, the reaction was carried out in usual way, in ethanol medium without cata-

lyst (Table 1, entry 1) followed by in neat condition (Table 1, entry 2) resulting poor yield. Reaction was also carried out

Table 1. Effect of different reaction parameters^a

Entry	Method	Solvent	Catalyst	Time	Temp. (°C)	Yield ^b (%)
1	Conventional	Ethanol	No	5 h	78	42
2	Conventional	Neat	No	1 h	80	30
3	Microwave	Neat	No	15 min	60	40
4	Microwave	Neat	AcOH	10 min	60	52
5	Microwave	Neat	Et ₃ N	10 min	60	55
6	Microwave	Neat	DABCO	10 min	60	50
7	Microwave	Neat	Nano-TiO ₂	10 min	60	58
8	Microwave	Neat	[DABCO-CH ₂ CH ₂ COOH] ⁺ [Br] ⁻	10 min	60	70
9	Microwave	Neat	Nano-TiO ₂ @[DABCO(CH ₂ CH ₂ COOH)] ⁺ [Br] ⁻	10 min	60	96
10	Microwave	Neat	Nano-TiO ₂ @[DABCO(-CH ₂ CH ₂ COOH)] ⁺ [Br] ⁻	10 min	80	89
11	Microwave	Neat	Nano-TiO ₂ @[DABCO(CH ₂ CH ₂ COOH)] ⁺ [Br] ⁻	10 min	30	81
12	Microwave	Neat	Nano-TiO ₂ @[DABCO(CH ₂ CH ₂ COOH)] ⁺ [Br] ⁻	5 min	60	88

^aReaction conditions: all reactions were carried out using 4-chloro thiophenol (1 mmol), phenyl glyoxal (1 mmol), para toluidine (1 mmol) and dimethyl acetylenedicarboxylate (1 mmol) under different reaction conditions. ^bIsolated yields.

under microwave irradiation in solvent-free and catalyst free manner (Table 1, entry 3). To improve the reaction yield, various catalysts were used like acidic AcOH (Table 1, entry 4), nano-TiO₂ (Table 1, entry 7) basic Et₃N (Table 1, entry 4), DABCO (Table 1, entry 6) resulting slight improvement in the yield. Then catalyst was varied with our synthesised catalyst (nano-TiO₂@[DABCO(CH₂CH₂COOH)]⁺[Br]⁻) under microwave-assisted solvent-free condition at 60°C and got most satisfactory result (Table 1, entry 9). Without altering catalyst, time and temperature of the reaction system was changed (Table 1, entry 10, 11, 12) but didn't get satisfactory yield. Finally it was observed that nano-TiO₂@[DABCO(CH₂CH₂COOH)]⁺[Br]⁻ catalysed microwave-assisted solvent-free condition at 60°C was the optimum reaction condition.

Catalyst loading: Subsequently, to determine the finest amount of catalyst required for the successful reaction, the reaction was conducted in the presence of miscellaneous amounts of catalyst, nano-TiO₂@[DABCO(CH₂CH₂COOH)]⁺[Br]⁻ (Fig. 4). In this catalyst loading graph, it has been revealed that with increasing amount of catalyst usage enhancement in the yield of the product occurs. It was up to 12 mol% of catalyst usage, more than which resulted no further improvement in product yield. In order to spend the least amount of catalyst, catalyst usage was restricted up to 12

Fig. 4. Yields at different catalyst loadings in the four component reaction of phenyl glyoxal, para toluidine, ethyl acetoacetate and dimedone.

mol%.

Substrate scope: With the optimized conditions in hand desired compounds are formed in two different ways with one reactant replacement (Table 2). In one way, various substituted or unsubstituted aromatic thiols, phenyl glyoxals (1 mmol), aromatic amines (1 mmol) and dialkyl acetylenedicarboxylates readily formed the desired compounds whereas in another way various substituted or unsubstituted aromatic thiols, phenyl glyoxals (1 mmol), aromatic amines (1 mmol) and β -keto ester readily formed the desired compounds. It was interesting to note that all the 4 components were varied with large extent of variety with very good to excellent yields.

Reaction mechanism: Considering the above experimental conclusions and the literature survey¹⁵ a rational reaction mechanism was proposed of the cascade reactions which are displayed in Scheme 2. Reaction begins with nucleophilic attack of aromatic amine towards β -keto ester for the formation of enamine compound C. On the other hand, aromatic thiol reacted with phenyl glyoxal for the formation of intermediate E followed by the reaction between intermediate C and intermediate F to form intermediate G. Next, this intermediate undergoes cyclisation and after the elimination of water, aromatization occurred and formed final product J. Here all the reaction steps were successfully catalysed by nano-TiO₂@[DABCO(CH₂CH₂COOH)]⁺[Br]⁻. Acidic surface of nano sized titania enhances the electrophilicity of carbonyl centre and carboxylic proton simultaneously acted as very good proton donor. Since here DABCO is monosubstituted, one of the two N centers is free along with lone pair of electron and other N centre is substituted with propionic acid. All along this mono substituted DABCO based ionic liquid shows amphoteric behaviour. Thus, owing to synergetic catalytic effect of the nano-TiO₂@[DABCO(CH₂CH₂COOH)]⁺[Br]⁻, the reactivity is increased largely from very beginning to end.

Using dialkylacetylenedicarboxylate, a different series of fully functionalised pyrrole derivatives were synthesized effectively. A rational reaction mechanism is displayed in Scheme 3, similar to Scheme 2. Primarily, the reaction begins with nucleophilic addition of aromatic amine towards the triple bond of dialkylacetylenedicarboxylate to form enamine A. In another case nucleophilic addition reaction in be-

Table 2. Structure of fully functionalised pyrrole compounds^a

Entry	R ¹	R ²	R ³	R ^{4/6}	R ⁵	Yield ^b
1	4-Cl	H	4-Me	CO ₂ Me	Me	91
2	4-Cl	H	4-OMe	CO ₂ Et	Et	93
3	H	H	3,4-di Me	CO ₂ Me	Me	85
4	4-Me	4-Me	3-Me	CO ₂ Me	Me	85
5	H	H	4-OMe	CO ₂ Me	Me	87
6	4-Me	H	4-Br	CO ₂ Et	Et	84
7	4-Me	4-Me	4-Cl	CO ₂ Et	Et	85
8	4-Me	4-OMe	4-Cl	CO ₂ Et	Et	84
9	4-Me	H	4-OMe	CO ₂ Et	Et	86
10	4-Me	H	4-Cl	CO ₂ Et	Et	89
11	4-Cl	4-Cl	4-OMe	CO ₂ Et	Et	90
12	H	H	H	Me	Me	88
13	4-Cl	4-Cl	4-Me	4-Me	Me	88
14	4-Me	4-Cl	2-Me	Me	Me	87
15	H	4-NO ₂	4-Me	Me	Me	95
16	4-Me	4-Me	4-Cl	Me	Me	88
17	4-Me	H	4-Br	Me	Et	84
18	4-Cl	H	4-Br	Me	Me	89
19	4-Cl	H	4-OMe	Me	Et	92
20	4-Me	H	4-OMe	Me	allyl	89
21	4-OMe	4-Cl	4-OMe	Me	allyl	94
22	4-Me	3-Br	4-Cl	Me	Me	90
23	butyl	H	2-Br	Me	Me	84
24	4-Me	4-Me	4-CO ₂ H	Me	Me	78
25	4-Cl	4-OMe	4-Br	Me	Me	89
26	4-OMe	H	3,4-di CH ₃	Me	Me	92
27	4-Cl	4-OMe	H	Me	Me	86

^aReaction conditions: all reactions were carried out using various substituted or unsubstituted aromatic thiols, phenyl glyoxals (1 mmol), aromatic amines (1 mmol) and dialkyl acetylenedicarboxylates or β-keto esters (1 mmol) under microwave-assisted 12 mol% nano-TiO₂@[DABCO(CH₂CH₂COOH)]⁺[Br]⁻ catalysed conditions. ^bIsolated yields.

tween aromatic thiol and phenyl glyoxal leads to formation of intermediate E followed by these two intermediates (C and E) went through condensation and synthesised intermediate G. Subsequently this intermediate G undergo cyclisation and aromatisation to form the final product J. Nano-

TiO₂@[DABCO(CH₂CH₂COOH)]⁺[Br]⁻ extremely influenced the reaction mechanism from very beginning to last step as shown in Scheme 3. Here TiO₂-NP and carboxylic group shows acidic character whereas unsubstituted tertiary nitrogen centre shows basic character. Thus as a consequence

Scheme 2. A rational reaction mechanism for the formation of nano-TiO₂@[DABCO(CH₂CH₂COOH)]⁺[Br]⁻ catalyzed fully functionalised pyrrole from β -keto ester, aromatic thiol, phenyl glyoxal and aromatic amine.

Mondal *et al.*: A synergistic effect of microwave irradiation and nano-TiO₂@[DABCO(CH₂CH₂CO₂H)]⁺[Br]⁻ for *etc.*

Scheme 3. A rational mechanistic pathway to explain the nano-TiO₂@[DABCO-CH₂CH₂COOH]⁺[Br]⁻ catalyzed formation of penta substituted pyrrole from dialkyl acetylenedicarboxylate, aromatic thiol, phenyl glyoxal and aromatic amine.

of synergetic catalytic effect of TiO_2 -NP and $[\text{DABCO}(\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{COOH})]^+[\text{Br}]^-$ reactivity largely enhanced.

Recycling Experiment

For examining recyclability of nano- TiO_2 @ $[\text{DABCO}(\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{COOH})]^+[\text{Br}]^-$ catalyst, for the formation of dimethyl 4-(4-chlorophenylthio)-5-phenyl-1-*p*-tolyl-1*H*-pyrrole-2,3-dicarboxylate (Table 2, entry 1) from the analogous starting materials under optimised conditions was considered as a model reaction. After completion of the reaction, the crude mixture was diluted with ethyl acetate (10 mL) and the catalyst was easily recovered by filtration using a sintered glass funnel. It was washed with ethyl acetate (5/10 mL) few more times to eliminate adhered organic compound and dried under vacuum. Next, to verify the activity of the catalyst, this recycling experiment was carried out using the recovered catalyst for the succeeding reactions. In a test of six cycles, it was observed that the catalyst could be reused with high catalytic activity (Fig. 5). After the recycling test, TEM analysis was also done. The result (Fig. 5) showed that there is no considerable alteration in morphology. These experiments have shown that nano- TiO_2 @ $[\text{DABCO}(\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{COOH})]^+[\text{Br}]^-$ had sufficient stability and could reproduce the product several times with almost similar efficiency.

Fig. 5. Recyclability test of the catalyst nano- TiO_2 @ $[\text{DABCO}(\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{COOH})]^+[\text{Br}]^-$.

Conclusions

This present protocol describes not only the expeditious but also solvent and chromatography-free synthesis of fully functionalised pyrrole moieties incorporating benzo-thio unit. Synergistic effects of microwave irradiation and nano- TiO_2 @ $[\text{DABCO}(\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{CO}_2\text{H})]^+[\text{Br}]^-$ catalyst have been highlighted here. This recyclable combined catalytic system shows unprecedented catalytic performance multiple times

with no loss of catalytic activity. Owing to simplicity of the procedure allied with environmentally benign features, it is hoped that this eco-compatible strategy will be embraced by the synthetic organic chemists at large.

Experimental section

General information of materials and instruments:

All the chemicals were availed from commercially accessible sources such as Aldrich, USA or Spectrochem, India or Rankem and used as received. Every reaction were performed in a closed reaction vessel under microwave irradiation using CEM Discover microwave reactor equipped with surface sensor for temperature measurement and controlled the reactions with setting time, temperature and power. The progress of the reactions was monitored by TLC checking. ^1H and ^{13}C NMR spectra were recorded on 300 MHz Bruker instrument using CDCl_3 or $\text{DMSO}-d_6$ as a solvent with tetramethylsilane (TMS) as internal reference. Chemical shifts are expressed in delta (δ) units in ppm and the data are represented as follows: for multiplicities s = singlet, d = doublet, t = triplet, q = quartet and m = multiplet and coupling constants in Hz and integration. Infrared spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer Spectrophotometer RX/FT-IR system in KBr pellets with absorptions in cm^{-1} and CHN analysis was performed using Perkin-Elmer 2400 Series II CHN analyzer. Melting points were determined on an electrical melting point apparatus with an open capillary and were uncorrected. HRMS were acquired using a Waters XEVO-G2S Q-TOF mass spectrometer with an ESI resource. Morphology and size of nano- TiO_2 @ $[\text{DABCO}(\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{CO}_2\text{H})]^+[\text{Br}]^-$ system was determined by acquiring SEM images using a Zeiss EVO18 (Special Edition). To monitor the actual size of TiO_2 -NPs covered with IL, TEM images were taken using a Jeol JEM 2010F transmission electron microscope operated at an accelerating voltage of 200 kV.

General procedure for the synthesis of DABCO based ionic liquid:

1,4-Diazobicyclo[2.2.2]octane (DABCO) (1 mmol) and 3-bromo propionic acid (1 mmol) were taken into a 10 ml round bottomed flask in anhydrous ethanol medium and then the mixture was refluxed for 2 h in an argon atmosphere. After completion of the reaction solvent was removed by rotor evaporator under reduced pressure. The synthesised ionic liquid was characterized by standard analytical techniques such as ^1H NMR, ^{13}C NMR.

Mondal *et al.*: A synergistic effect of microwave irradiation and nano-TiO₂@[DABCO(CH₂CH₂CO₂H)]⁺[Br]⁻ for *etc.*

General procedure for the synthesis of DABCO based ionic liquid embedded TiO₂ nanoparticles:

0.5 mmol titanium tetraisopropoxide was added to 10 ml ethanol and stirred in a covered flask for 10 min in 40 to 50°C (solution A). 1.5 mmol IL was dissolved into a mixture of 0.25 ml distilled water and 10 ml ethanol in a separate covered flask and stirred for 5 min (solution B). Then this titanium tetraisopropoxide solution (solution A) was added to sol B and vigorously stirred for another 1 hour in 100°C and then cooled to room temperature. Finally the ethanol was removed under vacuum and the resulting ionic liquid covered TiO₂-NP was obtained in powder form. The products were characterized by standard analytical techniques such as PXRD, SEM, TEM, TGA and DLS.

General procedure for the synthesis of pyrrole compounds:

In a closed reaction vial an equimolar mixture (1 mmol) of substituted and unsubstituted aryl thiol, aryl glyoxal, aromatic amine and dialkyl acetylenedicarboxylate or β-keto ester along with 10 mol% of nano-TiO₂@[DABCO-CH₂CH₂COOH]⁺[Br]⁻ was subjected to microwave irradiation at 60°C (100 W) for 10 min. After completion of this reaction, the reaction vial was cooled to room temperature. Then crude product mixture was diluted with 5 mL ethyl acetate. Thus a white solid product was slowly precipitate out after scratching few times the crude product with spatula and collected through simple filtration technique. Finally, a pure white product was obtained directly by recrystallization from ethyl acetate without using any chromatography methodology in good to excellent yields. All the synthesized compounds were characterized by ¹H, ¹³C NMR, IR, melting point measurements, CHN and HRMS analysis and the structure of the product was confirmed by single-crystal X-ray diffraction.

Characterization data of the product

Dimethyl 4-(4-chlorophenylthio)-5-phenyl-1-p-tolyl-1H-pyrrole-2,3-dicarboxylate (Table 1, entry 1): White solid (91%); m.p. 120°C (EtOAc); R_f [12% EtOAc/petroleum ether (60–80°C)]: 0.53; 6% EtOAc/petroleum ether (60–80°C) as eluent; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃): δ_H 7.18–7.03 (m, 13H, ArH), 3.80 (s, 3H, -OCH₃), 3.71 (s, 3H, -OCH₃), 2.30 (s, 3H, -CH₃); ¹³C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl₃): δ_C 165.1, 159.9, 142.7, 138.1, 137.0, 134.1, 130.8, 130.2, 129.0, 128.9, 128.3, 128.1, 128.0, 127.2, 126.0, 124.1, 109.0, 51.9, 52.0, 20.8 ppm; Anal.

Calcd. for C₂₇H₂₂ClNO₄S: C, 65.91; H, 4.51; N, 2.85. Found: C, 65.64; H, 4.59; N, 2.99.

Diethyl 4-(4-chlorophenylthio)-1-(4-methoxyphenyl)-5-phenyl-1H-pyrrole-2,3-dicarboxylate (Table 1, entry 2): White solid (93%); m.p. 126°C (EtOAc); R_f [12% EtOAc/petroleum ether (60–80°C)]: 0.40; 8% EtOAc/petroleum ether (60–80°C) as eluent; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃): δ_H 7.27–7.02 (m, 11H, ArH), 6.79–6.76 (m, 2H, ArH), 4.25 (q, J 7.2 Hz, 2H, -OCH₂), 4.14 (q, J 7.2 Hz, 2H, -OCH₂), 3.74 (s, 3H, -OCH₃), 1.22–1.13 (m, 6H, -CH₃); ¹³C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl₃): δ_C 164.4, 159.3, 143.5, 137.0, 130.8, 130.4, 130.1, 129.0, 129.0, 128.2, 128.0, 127.8, 127.4, 126.2, 124.1, 113.1, 108.2, 61.0, 59.7, 55.0, 13.6, 13.5 ppm; HRMS (ESI-TOF) *m/z*: [M+H]⁺ Calcd. for [C₂₉H₂₇ClNO₅S]: 536.1293, Found: 536.1296; IR (KBr, ν_{max} cm⁻¹): 3436, 2926, 1715, 1508, 125, 1200, 1028, 820 cm⁻¹; Anal. Calcd. for C₂₉H₂₆ClNO₅S: C, 64.98; H, 4.89; N, 2.61. Found: C, 64.70; H, 4.92; N, 2.77.

Dimethyl 1-(3,4-dimethylphenyl)-5-phenyl-4-(phenylthio)-1H-pyrrole-2,3-dicarboxylate (Table 1, entry 3): White solid (85%); m.p. 112°C (EtOAc); R_f [12% EtOAc/petroleum ether (60–80°C)]: 0.54; 6% EtOAc/petroleum ether (60–80°C) as eluent; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃): δ_H 7.22–7.01 (m, 10H, ArH), 6.90–6.85 (m, 2H, ArH), 3.77 (s, 3H, -OCH₃), 3.71 (s, 3H, -OCH₃), 2.20 (s, 3H, -CH₃), 2.14 (s, 3H, -CH₃) ppm; ¹³C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl₃): δ_C 165.0, 160.0, 143.5, 138.2, 136.8, 136.5, 135.0, 130.6, 129.2, 129.0, 128.5, 128.1, 128.0, 127.2, 126.9, 126.0, 125.0, 125.0, 124.0, 109.1, 52.0, 51.6, 19.2, 19.1 ppm; Anal. Calcd. for C₂₈H₂₅NO₄S: C, 71.32; H, 5.34; N, 2.97. Found: C, 71.20; H, 5.39; N, 3.10.

Dimethyl 1-m-tolyl-5-p-tolyl-4-(p-tolylthio)-1H-pyrrole-2,3-dicarboxylate (Table 1, entry 4): White solid (85%); m.p. 112°C (EtOAc); R_f [12% EtOAc/petroleum ether (60–80°C)]: 0.52; 8% EtOAc/petroleum ether (60–80°C) as eluent; ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃): δ_H 7.19–7.01 (m, 6H, ArH), 6.97–6.92 (m, 6H, ArH), 3.80 (s, 3H, -OCH₃), 3.69 (s, 3H, -OCH₃), 2.28 (s, 3H, -CH₃), 2.24 (s, 3H, -CH₃); ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃): δ_C 165.5, 160.2, 144.0, 138.5, 138.3, 137.8, 135.2, 135.0, 130.7, 129.6, 129.5, 129.3, 128.8, 128.5, 128.2, 126.9, 126.3, 125.4, 123.9, 110.1, 52.3, 52.0, 21.3, 21.2, 21.0 ppm; HRMS (ESI-TOF) *m/z*: [M+Na]⁺ Calcd. for [C₂₉H₂₇ClNO₄SNa]: 508.1553, Found: 508.1557; Anal. Calcd. for C₂₉H₂₇NO₄S: C, 71.70; H, 5.60; N, 2.88. Found: C, 71.58; H, 5.67; N, 3.04.

Dimethyl 1-(4-methoxyphenyl)-5-phenyl-4-(phenylthio)-1H-pyrrole-2,3-dicarboxylate (Table 1, entry 5): White solid

(87%); m.p. 112°C (EtOAc); R_f [15% EtOAc/petroleum ether (60–80°C)]: 0.52; 8% EtOAc/petroleum ether (60–80°C) as eluent; $^1\text{H NMR}$ (300 MHz, CDCl_3): δ_{H} 7.28–7.04 (m, 12H, ArH), 6.81–6.78 (m, 2H, ArH), 3.80 (s, 3H, $-\text{CH}_3$), 3.78 (s, 3H, $-\text{CH}_3$), 3.78 (s, 3H, $-\text{CH}_3$), 3.72 (s, 3H, $-\text{CH}_3$); $^{13}\text{C NMR}$ (75 MHz, CDCl_3): δ_{C} 165.3, 160.1, 159.3, 144.0, 134.8, 130.7, 130.7, 130.4, 129.2, 129.1, 128.7, 128.6, 128.4, 127.7, 127.6, 127.3, 127.2, 127.1, 126.7, 125.3, 124.2, 113.6, 113.5, 109.6, 55.3, 52.2, 52.0 ppm; Anal. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{27}\text{H}_{23}\text{NO}_5\text{S}$: C, 68.48; H, 4.90; N, 2.96. Found: C, 68.72; H, 4.83; N, 2.82.

Dimethyl diethyl 1-(4-bromophenyl)-5-phenyl-4-(p-tolylthio)-1H-pyrrole-2,3-dicarboxylate (Table 1, entry 6): White solid (84%); m.p. 112°C (EtOAc); R_f [12% EtOAc/petroleum ether (60–80°C)]: 0.50; 6% EtOAc/petroleum ether (60–80°C) as eluent; $^1\text{H NMR}$ (300 MHz, CDCl_3): δ_{H} 7.42–7.38 (m, 2H, ArH), 7.26–7.14 (m, 4H, ArH), 7.07–7.01 (m, 7H, ArH), 4.29 (q, J 7.2 Hz, 2H, $-\text{OCH}_2$), 4.17 (q, J 7.2 Hz, 2H, $-\text{OCH}_2$), 2.22 (s, 3H, $-\text{CH}_3$), 1.25–1.15 (m, 6H, $-\text{CH}_3$); $^{13}\text{C NMR}$ (75 MHz, CDCl_3): δ_{C} 164.5, 159.3, 143.4, 137.0, 135.4, 134.4, 131.6, 130.7, 129.7, 129.4, 128.9, 128.6, 128.3, 127.6, 122.1, 110.7, 61.4, 61.0, 20.7, 13.9, 13.5 ppm; Anal. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{29}\text{H}_{26}\text{BrNO}_4\text{S}$: C, 61.70; H, 4.64; N, 2.48. Found: C, 61.92; H, 4.59; N, 2.33.

Diethyl 1-(4-chlorophenyl)-5-p-tolyl-4-(p-tolylthio)-1H-pyrrole-2,3-dicarboxylate (Table 1, entry 7): White solid (85%); m.p. 118°C (EtOAc); R_f [12% EtOAc/petroleum ether (60–80°C)]: 0.52; 8% EtOAc/petroleum ether (60–80°C) as eluent; $^1\text{H NMR}$ (400 MHz, CDCl_3): δ_{H} 7.29–7.26 (m, 2H, ArH), 7.13–6.98 (m, 8H, ArH), 6.90–6.89 (m, 2H, ArH), 4.26 (q, J 7.2 Hz, 2H, $-\text{OCH}_2$), 4.17 (q, J 7.2 Hz, 2H, $-\text{OCH}_2$), 2.28 (s, 3H, $-\text{CH}_3$), 2.82 (s, 3H, $-\text{CH}_3$), 1.23–1.16 (m, 6H, $-\text{CH}_3$) ppm; $^{13}\text{C NMR}$ (100 MHz, CDCl_3): δ_{C} 135.0, 159.2, 144.0, 138.7, 136.3, 135.1, 134.7, 134.2, 130.7, 129.8, 129.5, 128.6, 128.5, 127.7, 126.0, 123.0, 110.5, 61.3, 61.0, 21.2, 21.0, 14.0, 13.8 ppm; HRMS (ESI-TOF) m/z : $[\text{M}+\text{H}]^+$ Calcd. for $[\text{C}_{30}\text{H}_{29}\text{ClNO}_4\text{S}]$: 534.1500, Found: 534.1507; Anal. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{30}\text{H}_{28}\text{ClNO}_4\text{S}$: C, 67.47; H, 5.28; N, 2.62. Found: C, 67.39; H, 5.24; N, 2.59.

Diethyl 1-(4-chlorophenyl)-5-(4-methoxyphenyl)-4-(p-tolylthio)-1H-pyrrole-2,3-dicarboxylate (Table 1, entry 8): White solid (84%); m.p. 114°C (EtOAc); R_f [12% EtOAc/petroleum ether (60–80°C)]: 0.49; 8% EtOAc/petroleum ether (60–80°C) as eluent; $^1\text{H NMR}$ (400 MHz, CDCl_3): δ_{H} 7.26 (d, J 8.4 Hz, 2H, ArH), 7.08–6.88 (m, 6H, ArH), 6.92 (d, J 8.8 Hz,

2H, ArH), 6.72 (d, J 8.8 Hz, 2H, ArH), 4.27 (q, J 7.2 Hz, 2H, $-\text{OCH}_2$), 4.14 (q, J 7.2 Hz, 2H, $-\text{OCH}_2$), 3.70 (s, 3H, $-\text{OCH}_3$), 2.25 (s, 3H, $-\text{CH}_3$), 1.20 (t, J 7.2 Hz, 3H, $-\text{CH}_3$), 1.16 (t, J 7.2 Hz, 3H, $-\text{CH}_3$); $^{13}\text{C NMR}$ (100 MHz, CDCl_3): δ_{C} 165.0, 159.4, 143.7, 136.4, 135.2, 134.3, 134.1, 132.0, 131.8, 129.3, 129.5, 128.8, 127.8, 122.9, 121.0, 112.0, 113.2, 110.0, 61.3, 60.5, 55.0, 21.0, 14.0, 13.8 ppm; Anal. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{30}\text{H}_{28}\text{ClNO}_5\text{S}$: C, 65.51; H, 5.13; N, 2.55. Found: C, 65.78; H, 5.03; N, 2.71.

Diethyl 1-(4-methoxyphenyl)-5-phenyl-4-(p-tolylthio)-1H-pyrrole-2,3-dicarboxylate (Table 1, entry 9): White solid (86%); m.p. 92°C (EtOAc); R_f [12% EtOAc/petroleum ether (60–80°C)]: 0.44; 8% EtOAc/petroleum ether (60–80°C) as eluent; $^1\text{H NMR}$ (400 MHz, CDCl_3): δ_{H} 7.18–7.10 (m, 2H, ArH), 7.04–6.95 (m, 8H, ArH), 6.76–6.72 (m, 2H, ArH), 4.22 (q, J 7.2 Hz, 2H, $-\text{OCH}_2$), 4.10 (q, J 7.2 Hz, 2H, $-\text{OCH}_2$), 3.71 (s, 3H, $-\text{OCH}_3$), 2.23 (s, 3H, $-\text{CH}_3$), 1.18 (t, J 7.2 Hz, 2H, $-\text{OCH}_2$), 1.15 (t, J 7.2 Hz, 3H, $-\text{CH}_3$); $^{13}\text{C NMR}$ (100 MHz, CDCl_3): δ_{C} 165.0, 159.5, 159.1, 139.7, 135.0, 134.6, 130.6, 130.4, 129.3, 129.1, 128.2, 127.5, 127.6, 127.2, 123.7, 113.4, 109.8, 61.1, 60.8, 55.1, 20.8, 13.9, 13.8 ppm; Anal. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{30}\text{H}_{29}\text{NO}_5\text{S}$: C, 69.88; H, 5.67; N, 2.72. Found: C, 69.66; H, 5.74; N, 2.89.

Diethyl 1-(4-chlorophenyl)-5-phenyl-4-(p-tolylthio)-1H-pyrrole-2,3-dicarboxylate (Table 1, entry 10): White solid (89%); m.p. 115°C (EtOAc); R_f [12% EtOAc/petroleum ether (60–80°C)]: 0.50; 6% EtOAc/petroleum ether (60–80°C) as eluent; $^1\text{H NMR}$ (300 MHz, CDCl_3): δ_{H} 7.25–7.03 (m, 13H, ArH), 4.27 (q, J 7.2 Hz, 2H, $-\text{OCH}_2$), 4.15 (q, J 7.05 Hz, 2H, $-\text{OCH}_2$), 2.26 (s, 3H, $-\text{CH}_3$), 1.24–1.15 (m, 6H, $-\text{CH}_3$); $^{13}\text{C NMR}$ (75 MHz, CDCl_3): δ_{C} 164.5, 159.0, 143.3, 136.4, 135.1, 134.2, 130.4, 129.2, 128.7, 128.4, 128.2, 128.0, 127.5, 122.9, 110.4, 61.1, 60.6, 20.6, 13.5, 13.6 ppm; HRMS (ESI-TOF) m/z : $[\text{M}+\text{H}]^+$ Calcd. for $[\text{C}_{29}\text{H}_{27}\text{ClNO}_4\text{S}]$: 520.1344, Found: 520.1349; IR (KBr, ν_{max} cm^{-1}): 3420, 2925, 1720, 1535, 1490, 1260, 1225, 1190, 1090 cm^{-1} ; Anal. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{29}\text{H}_{26}\text{ClNO}_4\text{S}$: C, 66.98; H, 5.04; N, 2.69. Found: C, 66.79; H, 5.05; N, 2.82.

Diethyl 5-(4-chlorophenyl)-4-(4-chlorophenylthio)-1-(4-methoxyphenyl)-1H-pyrrole-2,3-dicarboxylate (Table 1, entry 11): White solid (90 %); m.p. 110°C (EtOAc); R_f [15% EtOAc/petroleum ether (60–80°C)]: 0.40; 8% EtOAc/petroleum ether (60–80°C) as eluent; $^1\text{H NMR}$ (400 MHz, CDCl_3): δ_{H} 7.23–7.18 (m, 4H, ArH), 7.12–7.08 (m, 4H, ArH), 7.00–6.96 (m, 2H, ArH), 6.85–6.82 (m, 2H, ArH), 4.32 (q, J 7.2 Hz,

2H, -OCH₂), 4.20 (q, *J* 7.2 Hz, 2H, -OCH₂), 3.81 (s, 3H, -OCH₃), 1.27–1.20 (m, 6H, -CH₃); ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃): δ_C 165.0, 159.6, 160.0, 142.5, 137.2, 134.7, 131.7, 131.0, 130.0, 129.3, 128.8, 128.5, 128.2, 128.0, 127.2, 127.1, 125.2, 113.3, 109.1, 61.2, 55.4, 14.0, 13.9 ppm; HRMS (ESI-TOF) *m/z*: [M+H]⁺ Calcd. for [C₂₉H₂₆Cl₂NO₅S]: 570.0903, Found: 570.0900; Anal. Calcd. for C₂₉H₂₅Cl₂NO₅S: C, 61.06; H, 4.42; N, 2.46. Found: C, 61.36; H, 4.32; N, 2.34.

Methyl 2-methyl-1,5-diphenyl-4-(phenylthio)-1H-pyrrole-3-carboxylate (Table 1, entry 12): White solid (88%); m.p. 142°C (EtOAc); R_f [8% EtOAc/petroleum ether (60–80°C)]: 0.54; 2% EtOAc/petroleum ether (60–80°C) as eluent; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃): δ_H 7.28–7.09 (m, 15H, ArH), 3.60 (s, 3H, -OCH₃), 2.39 (s, 3H, -CH₃); ¹³C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl₃): δ_C 164.8, 139.5, 139.0, 137.8, 137.0, 130.0, 129.9, 128.4, 128.0, 127.7, 126.8, 125.3, 123.8, 114.0, 108.0, 50.1, 12.8 ppm; Anal. Calcd. for C₂₅H₂₁NO₂S: C, 75.16; H, 5.30; N, 3.51. Found: C, 75.39; H, 5.21; N, 3.28.

Methyl 5-(4-chlorophenyl)-4-(4-chlorophenylthio)-2-methyl-1-p-tolyl-1H-pyrrole-3-carboxylate (Table 1, entry 13): White solid (88%); m.p. 112°C (EtOAc); R_f [8% EtOAc/petroleum ether (60–80°C)]: 0.46; 3% EtOAc/petroleum ether (60–80°C) as eluent; ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃): δ_H 7.14–7.04 (m, 8H, ArH), 6.95–6.94 (m, 4H, ArH), 3.67 (s, 3H, -OCH₃), 2.38 (s, 3H, -CH₃), 2.30 (s, 3H, -CH₃); ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃): δ_C 164.8, 138.7, 138.6, 138.5, 138.3, 134.4, 133.4, 131.8, 130.0, 129.7, 129.0, 129.0, 128.7, 128.4, 128.0, 127.0, 127.0, 114.2, 108.2, 50.7, 20.8, 13.0 ppm; Anal. Calcd. for C₂₆H₂₁Cl₂NO₂S: C, 64.73; H, 4.39; N, 2.90. Found: C, 64.96; H, 4.34; N, 2.78.

Methyl 5-(4-chlorophenyl)-2-methyl-1-o-tolyl-4-(p-tolylthio)-1H-pyrrole-3-carboxylate (Table 1, entry 14): White solid (87%); m.p. 122°C (EtOAc); R_f [8% EtOAc/petroleum ether (60–80°C)]: 0.52; 3% EtOAc/petroleum ether (60–80°C) as eluent; ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃): δ_H 7.27–7.14 (m, 4H, ArH), 7.06–7.02 (m, 4H, ArH), 7.00–6.96 (m, 4H, ArH), 3.66 (s, 3H, -OCH₃), 2.27 (s, 3H, -CH₃), 2.25 (s, 3H, -CH₃); ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃): δ_C 165.2, 138.3, 138.0, 136.6, 136.4, 136.0, 134.1, 133.7, 131.6, 131.1, 129.3, 129.2, 129.1, 129.0, 127.8, 126.6, 125.8, 114.5, 109.2, 50.8, 21.0, 17.2, 12.6 ppm; Anal. Calcd. for C₂₇H₂₄ClNO₂S: C, 70.19; H, 5.24; N, 3.03. Found: C, 70.42; H, 5.15; N, 2.98.

Methyl 2-methyl-5-(4-nitrophenyl)-4-(phenylthio)-1-p-tolyl-1H-pyrrole-3-carboxylate (Table 1, entry 15): White solid

(95%); m.p. 208°C (EtOAc); R_f [8% EtOAc/petroleum ether (60–80°C)]: 0.48; 8% EtOAc/petroleum ether (60–80°C) as eluent; ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃): δ_H 7.94 (d, *J* 8.8 Hz, 2H, ArH), 7.24–6.92 (m, 11H ArH), 3.66 (s, 3H -OCH₃), 2.40 (s, 3H, -CH₃), 2.34 (s, 3H, -CH₃); ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃): δ_C 165.0, 146.3, 139.5, 139.2, 139.0, 137.2, 136.8, 134.2, 131.5, 131.2, 130.0, 128.5, 128.3, 128.0, 126.0, 125.6, 124.9, 122.7, 115.4, 110.6, 51.0, 21.0, 13.0 ppm; Anal. Calcd. for C₂₆H₂₂N₂O₄S: C, 68.10; H, 4.84; N, 6.11. Found: C, 67.90; H, 4.80; N, 6.20.

Methyl 1-(4-chlorophenyl)-2-methyl-5-p-tolyl-4-(p-tolylthio)-1H-pyrrole-3-carboxylate (Table 1, entry 16): White solid (88%); m.p. 120°C (EtOAc); R_f [8% EtOAc/petroleum ether (60–80°C)]: 0.54; 2% EtOAc/petroleum ether (60–80°C) as eluent; ¹H NMR (500 MHz, CDCl₃): δ_H 7.30 (d, *J* 8.5 Hz, 2H, ArH), 7.04–6.99 (m, 6H, ArH), 6.95–6.90 (m, 4H, ArH), 3.65 (s, 3H, -OCH₃), 2.38 (s, 3H, -CH₃), 2.27 (s, 3H, -CH₃), 2.24 (s, 3H, -CH₃); ¹³C NMR (125 MHz, CDCl₃): δ_C 165.2, 139.6, 137.9, 137.6, 136.8, 136.3, 134.3, 134.1, 130.7, 130.6, 129.8, 129.3, 129.3, 128.6, 127.4, 126.3, 115.0, 109.4, 96.2, 50.9, 21.3, 21.0, 13.2 ppm; Anal. Calcd. for C₂₇H₂₄ClNO₂S: C, 70.19; H, 5.24; N, 3.03. Found: C, 70.38; H, 5.21; N, 2.95.

Ethyl 1-(4-bromophenyl)-2-methyl-5-phenyl-4-(p-tolylthio)-1H-pyrrole-3-carboxylate (Table 1, entry 17): White solid (84%); m.p. 140°C (EtOAc); R_f [8% EtOAc/petroleum ether (60–80°C)]: 0.51; 3% EtOAc/petroleum ether (60–80°C) as eluent; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃): δ_H 7.49–7.46 (m, 2H, ArH), 7.19–6.99 (m, 11H, ArH), 4.19 (q, *J* 7.2 Hz, 2H, -OCH₂), 2.45 (s, 3H, -CH₃), 1.11 (t, *J* 7.05 Hz, 3H, -CH₃); ¹³C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl₃): δ_C 164.7, 139.4, 137.9, 136.8, 136.6, 133.8, 132.2, 130.7, 130.2, 129.9, 129.1, 127.6, 125.8, 122.2, 115.2, 109.1, 59.7, 20.8, 13.9, 13.0 ppm; HRMS (ESI-TOF) *m/z*: [M+H]⁺ Calcd. for [C₂₇H₂₅BrNO₂S]: 506.0784. Found 506.0789; IR (KBr, ν_{max} cm⁻¹): 3433, 2981, 1695, 1544, 1488, 1400, 1251, 1226, 1134, 1087, 840; Anal. Calcd. for C₂₇H₂₄BrNO₂S: C, 64.03; H, 4.78; N, 2.77. Found: C, 64.25; H, 4.76; N, 2.63.

Methyl 1-(4-bromophenyl)-4-(4-chlorophenylthio)-2-methyl-5-phenyl-1H-pyrrole-3-carboxylate (Table 1, entry 18): White solid (89%); m.p. 122°C (EtOAc); R_f [8% EtOAc/petroleum ether (60–80°C)]: 0.48; 3% EtOAc/petroleum ether (60–80°C) as eluent; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃): δ_H 7.46 (d, *J* 8.4 Hz, 2H, ArH), 7.26–7.14 (m, 5H, ArH), 7.07–6.96 (m,

6H, ArH), 3.69 (s, 3H, -CH₃), 2.41 (s, 3H, -CH₃); ¹³C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl₃): δ_C 165.1, 139.9, 139.1, 138.3, 136.6, 132.5, 130.8, 130.3, 130.2, 130.1, 128.7, 128.1, 128.0, 122.6, 115.0, 108.8, 51.1, 13.3 ppm; Anal. Calcd. for C₂₅H₁₉BrClNO₂S: C, 58.55; H, 3.73; N, 2.73. Found: C, 58.72; H, 3.68; N, 2.60.

Ethyl 4-(4-chlorophenylthio)-1-(4-methoxyphenyl)-2-methyl-5-phenyl-1H-pyrrole-3-carboxylate (Table 1, entry 19): White solid (92%); m.p. 128°C (EtOAc); R_f [10% EtOAc/petroleum ether (60–80°C)]: 0.49; 5% EtOAc/petroleum ether (60–80°C) as eluent; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃): δ_H 7.19–7.01 (m, 11H, ArH), 6.86–6.83 (m, 2H, ArH), 4.18 (q, *J* 7.2 Hz, 2H, -OCH₂), 3.79 (s, 3H, -OCH₃), 2.43 (s, 3H, -CH₃), 1.10 (t, *J* 7.2 Hz, 3H, -CH₃); ¹³C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl₃): δ_C 164.8, 159.2, 140.1, 139.6, 138.8, 130.7, 130.5, 130.1, 129.7, 129.3, 128.4, 127.6, 127.6, 126.8, 114.5, 114.2, 107.2, 59.6, 55.3, 13.9, 13.0 ppm; Anal. Calcd. for C₂₇H₂₄ClNO₃S: C, 67.84; H, 5.06; N, 2.93. Found: C, 67.70; H, 5.04; N, 3.02.

Allyl 4-(4-chlorophenylthio)-1-(4-methoxyphenyl)-2-methyl-5-phenyl-1H-pyrrole-3-carboxylate (Table 1, entry 20): White solid (89%); m.p. 126°C (EtOAc); R_f [8% EtOAc/petroleum ether (60–80°C)]: 0.49; 4% EtOAc/petroleum ether (60–80°C) as eluent; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃): δ_H 7.27–7.02 (m, 11H, ArH), 6.86–6.83 (m, 2H, ArH), 5.83–5.74 (m, 1H, -CH), 5.32–5.26 (m, 1H, -OCH₂), 4.66–4.64 (m, 2H, -CH₂), 3.79 (s, 3H, -OCH₃), 2.44 (s, 3H, -CH₃), 2.29 (s, 3H, -CH₃); ¹³C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl₃): δ_C 164.6, 159.1, 139.9, 138.7, 137.0, 133.8, 132.6, 130.8, 130.7, 130.2, 129.4, 129.1, 127.5, 126.0, 117.3, 114.2, 114.1, 108.6, 64.4, 55.3, 20.8, 13.1 ppm; IR (KBr, ν cm⁻¹): 3423, 2925, 1706, 1546, 1514, 1400, 1251, 1220, 1070, 1488, 1400; Anal. Calcd. for C₂₈H₂₄ClNO₃S: C, 68.63; H, 4.94; N, 2.86. Found: C, 68.40; H, 4.91; N, 2.98.

Allyl 5-(4-chlorophenyl)-1-(4-methoxyphenyl)-4-(4-methoxyphenylthio)-2-methyl-1H-pyrrole-3-carboxylate (Table 1, entry 21): White solid (94%); m.p. 136°C (EtOAc); R_f [10% EtOAc/petroleum ether (60–80°C)]: 0.41; 5% EtOAc/petroleum ether (60–80°C) as eluent; ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃): δ_H 7.11–7.06 (m, 4H, ArH), 7.02–6.98 (m, 4H, ArH), 6.83 (d, *J* 8.8 Hz, 2H, ArH), 6.74 (d, *J* 8.8 Hz, 2H, ArH), 5.88–5.79 (m, 1H, -CH), 5.33–5.28 (m, 1H, -CH₂), 5.15–5.12 (m, 1H, -CH₂), 4.66 (d, *J* 5.6 Hz, 2H, -CH₂), 3.76 (s, 3H, -OCH₃), 3.72 (s, 3H, -OCH₃), 2.38 (s, 3H, -OCH₃); ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃): δ_C ppm 164.5, 159.3, 157.5, 138.9, 138.2, 133.5, 132.7, 132.2, 130.7, 130.0, 129.4, 129.4, 128.4, 128.0,

127.9, 117, 114.4, 114.3, 110.4, 64.6, 55.4, 55.3, 13.2; Anal. Calcd. for C₂₉H₂₆ClNO₄S: C, 66.98; H, 5.04; N, 2.69. Found: C, 66.78; H, 4.99; N, 2.75.

Methyl 5-(3-bromophenyl)-1-(4-chlorophenyl)-2-methyl-4-(p-tolylthio)-1H-pyrrole-3-carboxylate (Table 1, entry 22): White solid (90%); m.p. 115°C (EtOAc); R_f [8% EtOAc/petroleum ether (60–80°C)]: 0.46; 8% EtOAc/petroleum ether (60–80°C) as eluent; ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃): δ_H 7.35–7.26 (9m, 3H, ArH), 7.19 (bs, 1H, ArH), 7.07–6.99 (m, 7H, ArH), 6.95–6.93 (m, 1H, ArH), 3.69 (s, 3H, -OCH₃), 2.38 (s, 3H, -CH₃), 2.27 (s, 3H, -CH₃); ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃): δ_C 165.1, 138.4, 137.4, 135.9, 135.7, 134.6, 134.5, 133.6, 132.3, 130.7, 129.6, 129.5, 129.5, 129.3, 129.3, 129.2, 126.7, 121.6, 115.0, 110.8, 51.0, 20.9, 13.1 ppm; Anal. Calcd. for C₂₆H₂₁BrClNO₂S: C, 59.27; H, 4.02; N, 2.66. Found: C, 59.11; H, 4.08; N, 2.76.

Methyl 4-(butylthio)-2-methyl-1,5-diphenyl-1H-pyrrole-3-carboxylate (Table 1, entry 23): White solid (84%); m.p. 106°C (EtOAc); R_f [8% EtOAc/petroleum ether (60–80°C)]: 0.60; 2% EtOAc/petroleum ether (60–80°C) as eluent; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃): δ_H 7.29–7.26 (m, 2H, ArH), 7.16–7.01 (m, 7H, ArH), 3.90 (s, 3H, -CH₃), 2.64 (t, *J* 7.2 Hz, 3H, -CH₃), 2.32 (s, 3H, -CH₃), 0.72 (t, *J* 7.2 Hz, 3H, -CH₃); ¹³C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl₃): δ_C 165.5, 138.2, 137.3, 137.1, 131.0, 128.6, 128.1, 128.0, 127.1, 127.0, 114.2, 112.0, 50.6, 36.1, 30.7, 21.3, 13.2, 12.8 ppm; Anal. Calcd. for C₂₃H₂₅NO₂S: C, 72.79; H, 6.64; N, 3.69. Found: C, 72.89; H, 6.60; N, 3.52.

4-(3-(Methoxycarbonyl)-2-methyl-5-p-tolyl-4-(p-tolylthio)-1H-pyrrol-1-yl)benzoic acid (Table 1, entry 24): White solid (78%); m.p. 138°C (EtOAc); R_f [40% EtOAc/petroleum ether (60–80°C)]: 0.45; 15% EtOAc/petroleum ether (60–80°C) as eluent; ¹H NMR (500 MHz, CDCl₃): δ_H 7.91 (d, *J* 8 Hz, 2H, ArH), 7.38 (d, *J* 8 Hz, 2H, ArH), 7.02–6.92 (m, 8H, ArH), 3.53 (s, 3H, -OCH₃), 2.28 (s, 3H, -CH₃), 2.17 (s, 3H, -CH₃), 2.13 (s, 3H, -CH₃); ¹³C NMR (125 MHz, CDCl₃): δ_C 166.7, 164.4, 141.0, 139.8, 137.8, 137.2, 136.6, 134.0, 131.0, 130.6, 130.3, 129.4, 129.1, 128.6, 127.4, 125.6, 114.2, 108.0, 51.0, 21.0, 20.6, 13.0 ppm; Anal. Calcd. for C₂₈H₂₅NO₄S: C, 71.32; H, 5.34; N, 2.97. Found: C, 71.10; H, 5.38; N, 3.07.

Methyl 1-(4-bromophenyl)-4-(4-chlorophenylthio)-5-(4-methoxyphenyl)-2-methyl-1H-pyrrole-3-carboxylate (Table 1, entry 25): White solid (89%); m.p. 122°C (EtOAc); R_f [8% EtOAc/petroleum ether (60–80°C)]: 0.42; 4% EtOAc/petro-

leum ether (60–80°C) as eluent; ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃): δ_H 7.44 (d, *J* 8.4 Hz, 2H, ArH), 7.12 (d, *J* 8.4 Hz, 2H, ArH), 7.03 (d, *J* 8.4 Hz, 2H, ArH), 3.65 (s, 6H, -OCH₃), 2.36 (s, 3H, -CH₃); ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃): δ_C 165.0, 159.1, 139.5, 139.1, 138.0, 136.5, 132.2, 131.8, 129.9, 129.8, 128.2, 127.0, 122.2, 122.1, 114.5, 113.2, 108.1, 55.0, 50.7, 13.1 ppm; Anal. Calcd. for C₂₆H₂₁BrClNO₃S: C, 57.52; H, 3.90; N, 2.58. Found: C, 57.26; H, 3.95; N, 2.70.

Methyl 1-(3,4-dimethylphenyl)-4-(4-methoxyphenylthio)-2-methyl-5-phenyl-1H-pyrrole-3-carboxylate (Table 1, entry 26): White solid (92%); m.p. 130°C (EtOAc); R_f [10% EtOAc/petroleum ether (60–80°C)]: 0.51; 4% EtOAc/petroleum ether (60–80°C) as eluent; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃): δ_H 7.15–7.03 (m, 8H, ArH), 6.87–6.74 (m, 4H, ArH), 3.72 (s, 3H, -OCH₃), 3.71 (s, 3H, -OCH₃), 2.38 (s, 3H, -CH₃), 2.17 (s, 3H, -CH₃); ¹³C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl₃): δ_C 165.1, 157.1, 139.1, 138.0, 137.0, 136.4, 135.0, 130.8, 130.6, 129.5, 129.0, 128.2, 127.1, 125.4, 113.8, 109.6, 54.9, 50.5, 19.3, 19.2, 12.8 ppm; Anal. Calcd. for C₂₈H₂₇NO₃S: C, 73.49; H, 5.95; N, 3.06. Found: C, 73.72; H, 5.91; N, 2.87.

Methyl 4-(4-chlorophenylthio)-5-(4-methoxyphenyl)-2-methyl-1-phenyl-1H-pyrrole-3-carboxylate (Table 1, entry 27): White solid (86%); m.p. 100°C (EtOAc); R_f [10% EtOAc/petroleum ether (60–80°C)]: 0.44; 6% EtOAc/petroleum ether (60–80°C) as eluent; ¹H NMR (500 MHz, CDCl₃): δ_H 7.30 (bs, 3H, ArH), 7.14–7.04 (m, 6H, ArH), 6.91 (d, *J* 8.5 Hz, 2H, ArH), 6.63 (d, *J* 8.85 Hz, 2H, ArH), 3.66 (s, 3H, -OCH₃), 3.66 (s, 3H, -OCH₃), 2.37 (s, 3H, -CH₃); ¹³C NMR (125 MHz, CDCl₃): δ_C 164.8, 158.8, 139.6, 139.1, 138.0, 137.4, 129.7, 128.1, 122.5, 114.1, 107.4, 54.8, 50.6, 13.0 ppm; Anal. Calcd. for C₂₆H₂₂ClNO₃S: C, 67.30; H, 4.78; N, 3.02. Found: C, 67.54; H, 4.76; N, 2.89.

Acknowledgements

One of the authors (PM) would like to thank CAS-V (UGC), DSTFIST and DST-PURSE, Department of Chemistry, University of Calcutta for funding as departmental projects.

References

- (a) Kokel, C. Schafer and B. Torok, *Green Chem.*, 2017, **19**, 3729; (b) V. Sadhasivam, R. Balasaravanan and A. Siva, *Appl. Organometal Chem.*, 2019, **33**, e4994.
- U. R. Pillai, E. S. Demessie and R. S. Varma, *Green Chem.*, 2004, **6**, 295.
- (a) Pedro, N. Romano, J. M. A. R. D. Almeida, Y. Carvalho, P. Priece, E. F. S. Aguiar and J. A. L. Sanchez, *ChemSusChem.*, 2016, **9**, 3387; (b) T. Razzaq and C. O. Kappe, *ChemSusChem.*, 2008, **1**, 123.
- H. Cho, F. Torok and B. Torok, *Green Chem.*, 2014, **16**, 3623.
- (a) J. Restrepo, P. Lozano, M. I. Burguete, E. G. Verdugo and S. V. Luis, *Catal. Today*, 2015, **255**, 97; (b) D. Zhang, C. Zhou and R. Wang, *Catal. Commun.*, 2012, **22**, 83; (c) A. Karakulina, A. Gopakumar, I. Akaok, B. L. Roulier, T. Lagrange, S. A. Katsyuba, S. Das and P. J. Dyson, *Angew. Chem.*, 2016, **128**, 300.
- (a) A. Ying, Z. Li, J. Yang, S. Liu, S. Xu, H. Yan and C. Wu, *J. Org. Chem.*, 2014, **79**, 6510; (b) N. Seyyedi, F. Shirini, M. Safarpour and N. Langarudi, *RSC Adv.*, 2016, **6**, 44630.
- (a) A. Banerjee, R. Theron and R. W. J. Scott, *ChemSusChem.*, 2012, **5**, 109; (b) A. J. Reay and I. J. S. Fairlamb, *Chem. Commun.*, 2015, **51**, 16289; (c) A. Amoozadeh, S. Rahmani, M. Bitaraf, F. B. Abadi and E. Tabrizian, *New J. Chem.*, 2016, **40**, 770.
- (a) J. Arras, M. Steffan, Y. Shayeghi and P. Claus, *Chem. Commun.*, 2008, 4058; (b) J. Arras, M. Steffan, Y. Shayeghi, D. Ruppert and P. Claus, *Green Chem.*, 2009, **11**, 716; (c) C. P. Mehnert, R. A. Cook, N. C. Dispenziere and M. Afeworki, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2002, **124**, 12932.
- P. N. Romano, J. M. A. R. D. Almeida, Y. Carvalho, P. Priece, E. F. S. Aguiar and J. A. L. Sanchez, *ChemSusChem.*, 2016, **9**, 3387.
- T. Vivekanand, P. Vinoth, B. Agieshkumar, N. Sampath, A. Sudalai, J. C. Menéndez and V. Sridharan, *Green Chem.*, 2015, **17**, 3415.
- D. Imbri, N. Netz, M. Kucukdisli, L. M. Kammer, P. Jung, A. Kretzschmann and T. Opatz, *J. Org. Chem.*, 2014, **79**, 11750.
- (a) F. Chen, T. Shen, Y. Cui and N. Jiao, *Org. Lett.*, 2012, **14**, 4926; (b) B. Emayavaramban, M. Sen and B. Sundararaju, *Org. Lett.*, 2017, **19**, 6.
- (a) G. C. Nandi and K. Soumini, *J. Org. Chem.*, 2016, **81**, 11909; (b) V. Estevez, M. Villacampa and J. C. Menendez, *Chem. Soc. Rev.*, 2010, **39**, 4402.
- Z. Gong, Yu Lei, P. Zhou and Z. Zhang, *New J. Chem.*, 2017, **41**, 10613.
- (a) P. Mondala, S. Chatterjee, K. Nurjamal, S. Maity, A. Bhaumik, G. Brahmachari, P. Ghosh and C. Mukhopadhyay, *Catal. Commun.*, 2020, **139**, 105966; (b) P. Mondal, S. Chatterjee, A. Bhaumik, S. Maity, Prasanta Ghosh and C. Mukhopadhyay, *ChemistrySelect*, 2019, **4**, 3140.

